

Assessing the impact of private school groups on student academic achievement

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Abstract

This study assesses the impact of private school groups' acquisition of schools on the examination results of Key Stages 4 & 5 students in England, a previously unexplored area. Utilising GOV.UK data for the years 2012-2024 (excluding 2021-22 due to COVID), a staggered difference-in-differences approach was employed to evaluate the impact private school groups have on GCSE and A-Level results. The analysis revealed a statistically and economically significant decrease in the average grade across Key Stage 5, particularly in high-achieving students, compared with a negligible impact on average grade at Key Stage 4 but a moderate negative impact on pass rates. Crucially, the study finds school groups have a significant negative effect inside London compared with the remainder of England.

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1 Introduction

The debate over optimal market structure, policies and incentives to best support educational outcomes is ongoing. Education in England requires improvement; approximately 18% and 21% of adults have low literacy and numeracy levels respectively (OECD, 2024). A significant recent trend has emerged in England and globally where businesses, backed by institutional investors, are acquiring collections of private schools thereby forming private school groups. This has introduced a new educational model with unclear objectives - to deliver optimal educational outcomes or simply maximise profit?

Despite the growing presence of these groups, to date no research has been completed regarding their impact on academic achievement in England. This study aims to address this gap by employing a staggered difference-in-differences approach to determine what effect private school groups have on academic attainment. Specifically, this study examines the impact on pass rates, high grades awarded and average grades. This study focuses on Key Stages 4 and 5 (“KS4” and “KS5”) results which are evaluated in years 11 and 13 (ages 16 and 18) through GCSEs and A-Levels respectively. Untreated independent schools serve as the control group to mitigate selection bias¹.

From an economic standpoint, analysing examination results offers insight into the human capital formation process during a critical age of schooling. Human Capital Theory explains why investments into education are essential for individuals to increase their economic value and productivity which more widely contributes to economic growth (Barro, 2013; Becker, 1964; Hanushek and Woessmann, 2008).

This study aims to assess whether the unique characteristics and structure of private school groups are associated with higher educational quality, to increase information for regulators, such as the Independent Schools Inspectorate and the Competition and Markets Authority, as well as the Department of Education². This

¹ This equates to 6-7% of students in England (Sibieta, 2023)

² Department of Education is responsible for all UK schools.

study's results may guide policy decisions on regulating the growth of private school groups, regulating market concentration, supporting parental choice, and shaping broader policies on school structure and governance to ensure high-quality education across all schools in England.

This study presents mixed findings. At KS4, a moderate decline in pass rates is present alongside a small improvement in high grades, with an overarching negligible impact on the average grade. In contrast, at KS5, reverse effects are present; a small improvement in pass rates and a significant decline in high grades awarded, resulting in an overall decline of half a grade on average. Importantly, the analysis highlights regional variation, with acquisitions inside London producing statistically significantly larger negative effects on attainment compared to outside. To ensure robustness, a comprehensive set of sensitivity tests are conducted including adding controls, using an unrestricted control group and comparing results of core subjects exclusively.

To contextualise these findings, this study draws on literature related to similar autonomous school systems, such as US charter schools, UK academies and various voucher programmes. The literature review assesses which policies and school characteristics are consistently associated with improved outcomes and how regional disparities influence these effects.

Conclusively, the results suggest that the private school group model provides an ineffective framework in improving attainment. However, private school groups remain relatively new. As they continue to grow, additional data and research is needed to confirm these results. Moreover, individual groups' models differ in structure, size, global presence and policy which may have different impacts on attainment uncaptured by this study. Finally, attainment only represents one section of educational quality; broader aspects such as character development, extra-curricular skills and holistic student growth could be considered.

1.1 Institutional Setup

Throughout the past two decades, the global education market has undergone significant change. Institutional investors, notably private equity, have invested

heavily into businesses that acquire and manage private schools. While there is no formal definition of a private school group, within this study a private school group is defined as a privately incorporated for-profit company that owns five or more independent schools worldwide. Furthermore, to be included within this study a school must be located in England and teach Key Stage 4 or 5³.

KS4 is defined as the two years of schooling between ages 14 and 16, where students must take Maths, English and Science GCSEs but have choice over other subjects or alternative qualifications such as BTECs; students usually take around 10 examinations (UCAS, 2025). KS5 is defined as the two years of schooling following KS4 between the ages of 16 and 18. Legally, students must be in some form of education at this stage with most students sitting A-Level qualifications.

Figure 1: School Groups as a Proportion of English Schools

Notes: English Schools only, all school consists of both Key Stage 4 and 5. KS4 = Key Stage 4 and KS5 = Key Stage 5. Authors calculation using data from Education Investor (2025), MarketIQ (2025) and Companies House (2025).

Merger and acquisition activity has increased since 2012, causing a consistent upward trend of English schools being owned by a school group, evidenced by Figure 1. The growth of private school groups is mainly driven by continued investment. Institutional investors search for markets with stable demand, resilience, and growth potential. Blundell *et al.* (2010) found a one standard

³ Table A.1 details all private school groups, the number of schools they own, and their institutional investor included within this study.

deviation increase in private school fees equates to an elasticity of -0.26, demonstrating private schools are price inelastic indicating stable demand⁴. Even with the introduction of VAT on private schools, Sibieta (2023) only expects a decrease of between 3-7% in admissions. Additionally, the education market's profit grew 6.9% annually over the past 5 years and the revenue is forecast to have a 2.0% compound annual growth rate until 2030 (IBIS, 2024) indicating strong growth potential.

English private school groups are for-profit and are fully autonomous meaning they have control over policies, structure and personnel. They claim to deliver academic excellence as well as building well-rounded children and do this through creating a great learning environment, but none explain directly how this is done. However, they emphasise a range of policies they implement to maximise educational quality. These include creating a network to share expertise and best practice between staff, large investments, forming an international student community, offering extracurricular activities, incorporating technology into education, increasing parental engagement, expert leadership and school governance from proven professionals, and creating a social purpose.⁵ (Cognita, 2025; Dukes Education, 2025; Nord Anglia Education, 2025; Forfar Education, 2025; Wishford, 2025; Inspired Education, 2025). Additionally, private school groups are impacted by a range of economic factors including economies of scale, market structure, incentives, and human capital.

Economies of Scale

One theoretical economic justification of private school groups is the benefit from economies of scale. Synergies emerge through combining back-office functions such as accounting and HR, sharing teacher training, or bulk purchasing of resources. Lubienski and Lubienski (2014) found US charter school networks

⁴ All schools owned by private school groups are independent schools, but not all independent schools are owned by private school groups.

⁵ This summary across all private school groups, some cited groups do not claim certain policies or traits.

benefited from lower administrative costs enabling reinvestment which is associated with moderate performance improvements.

However, when groups become large, diseconomies of scale can emerge through reduced responsiveness to school-level requirements, bureaucratic inefficiencies, or excessive centralisation. Large multi-academy trusts (“MATs”) in England that manage over fifteen schools proved no significant advantage over independent academies (Greany and Higham, 2018) attributable to MATs low flexibility and responsiveness to local needs (Eyles and Machin, 2019). Andrews *et al.* (2002) found excessive centralisation led to reduced school autonomy causing lower efficiency in US charters.

Market Structure

Traditionally, independent schools have operated individually resembling monopolistic competition, such that differentiation in curriculum, enrichment opportunities and school policy varies demand (Hoxby, 2000). However, the consolidation through school groups could shift the market structure towards an oligopoly, where schools do not differentiate thus limiting parental choice, reducing competition, and removing the incentive to improve educational quality. Empirically, private school consolidation in Chile led to increased segmentation rather than improved quality (Urquiola, 2005).

Profit and Quality Incentives

A profit incentive introduces concerns regarding educational quality being sacrificed for financial return. Literature suggests for-profit US charters are associated with lower attainment compared to not-for-profits because not-for-profits reinvest in education while for-profits cut costs through lower staff salaries and larger classes (Lubienski and Brewer, 2016; Miron and Urschel, 2010).

The issue is more significant in oligopolistic markets where reduced competition decreases the requirement for schools to attract students through quality. Empirically, profit-maximising behaviours harm student attainment (Bettinger, 2005; Bifulco and Ladd, 2004; Angrist *et al.*, 2013), although Hsieh and Urquiola

(2006) highlights in Chile this may reflect selective admissions rather than lower quality.

Human Capital

High-quality human capital is crucial for high academic attainment (Rivkin *et al.*, 2005). Private school groups emphasise their support network of professionals and proven teacher training programmes; centralised professional development programmes have had proven success with US charter schools (Dobbie and Fryer, 2013).

However, over-centralisation can restrict school-level autonomy; within MATs, structured professional development programmes were beneficial but excessive centralisation led to lower teacher satisfaction and innovation (Mujis *et al.*, 2021).

2 Literature Review

To the best of my knowledge, at the time this research no other studies have investigated the impact of private school groups in England on academic attainment. However, private school groups are comparable to alternative education markets with autonomous schools; research can be examined to extract the policies and characteristics that drive high educational quality.

Impact of Autonomous Schools

Irmert *et al.* (2024), in a holistic study of autonomous schools in fifteen countries across 16 years, found little evidence they positively impact students. Similarly, US Charter schools, UK academies and voucher systems yield mixed attainment outcomes. Urban US Charters in cities such as Boston and New York demonstrate improved results (Hoxby and Murarka, 2009; Dobbie and Fryer, 2011; Abdulkadiroglu *et al.*, 2011), especially for low-income, low-achievers and ethnic minority students (Angrist *et al.*, 2013; Gleason *et al.*, 2010). Comparatively, other studies found negligible or negative effects in US charters (Bettinger, 2005; Lubienski and Lubienski, 2014). However, this is arguably attributed to methodological approach where lottery-based admissions show stronger effects

than broad multi-state analysis incorporating underachieving charters (Zimmer *et al.*, 2009; CREDO, 2013).

Early UK academies modestly improved GCSE results, especially for disadvantaged students (Andrews and Perera, 2017) but post-2010, when higher-achieving schools began undergoing conversion, results became indistinguishable to maintained schools (Education Policy Institute, 2017; Eyles *et al.*, 2018). This evidences academisation does not inherently improve outcomes (Gorard, 2014; Machin and Veroit, 2011). Columbian voucher systems illustrate positive effects (Angrist, 2002) while in Chile and Sweden negative effects are present unless paired with strong regulation, accountability, and quality controls (Parry, 2006; Hsieh and Urquiola, 2006).

Impact of Size

Theoretically, larger school groups show potential through utilising economies of scale, best practices and networks. Positive impacts of Swedish voucher schools are attributed to groups spreading best practices (Böhlmark and Lindahl, 2015). Dobbie and Fryer (2011) demonstrate how US charter networks offer strong support and structure, however, excessive stratification and rapid expansion with no quality controls in Chile's voucher system led to minimal gains (Hsieh and Urquiola, 2006; Bellei, 2009).

Similarly, while trusts are preferred to run multiple English academies because of the theoretical advantages, Haves (2023) explains multi-academy trusts have suffered from inconsistency in leadership, rapid expansion, and poor resource distribution.

Autonomous Schools' Effective Policies

Certain policies that autonomous schools introduce are correlated with greater attainment. Specifically, within US charters, extended teaching hours, higher teacher autonomy, increased parental engagement and better feedback systems (Dobbie and Fryer, 2013; Angrist *et al.*, 2016) are associated with achievement increases of 0.2 standard deviations (Hoxby and Murarka, 2009), especially

benefiting disadvantaged students (Angrist *et al.*, 2013). Similarly, strong leadership, increased funding, and targeted interventions empirically prove effective in UK academies (Andrews and Perera, 2017).

Notably, the ‘no excuses’ discipline where students are held accountable with strict behavioural expectations is positively correlated with academic performance, again, especially with disadvantaged pupils (Angrist *et al.*, 2013). However, critics argue this may suppress critical thinking skills and intellectual curiosity thus decreasing educational quality (Miron *et al.*, 2011; Cullen *et al.*, 2005).

Voucher schools only benefit from being autonomous when paired with greater accountability, stricter discipline, and high-quality teachers (Elacqua, 2012; Lindbom, 2010; OECD, 2018). Chile’s merit-based pay schemes were strongly correlated with higher attainment (Behrman *et al.*, 2016) but these systems may increase educational inequality (Hsieh and Urquiola, 2006). Voucher systems without these characteristics did not raise achievement (Hsieh and Urquiola, 2006).

Regional Impact

In both US charters and UK academies, schools within urban areas generally outperform rural schools (Zimmer *et al.*, 2009; Cohodes, 2018; Andrews and Perera, 2017). This is due to greater competition, high-quality teachers, and access to resources (Dobbie and Fryer, 2011; Andrews and Perera, 2017). However, positive effects in US charters may reflect closures of public schools which in turn may have artificially inflated urban findings (Zimmer *et al.*, 2009; Cullen *et al.*, 2005).

Similarly, voucher schools perform better in urban regions, specifically in Chile where rural schools exhibited minimal gains because of fewer choices and lower competition (Contreras *et al.*, 2010).

3 Data and Descriptive Statistics

The primary data source used in this study has been sourced from the GOV.UK website⁶ which is publicly available. The dataset provides annual Key Stage 4 and 5 results broken down by school, qualification, and subject in England from 1991 to 2024. In addition, the results dataset includes Pupil Census Data. This contains school-level data such as school location, special educational needs, gender split, selective status, and school size. This provides additional contextual information about schools and their pupil populations to further this study's analysis.

The raw dataset consists of annual breakdowns of individual Key Stage results detailing number of results by grade, qualification, subject, and unique reference number ("URN") which is used to identify schools. The data was cleaned by refining the results to include only GCSE (KS4) and A-Level (KS5) qualifications from the years 2012 to 2024, calculating dependent variables of pass rates, high grades awarded and the average grade. Data from 2020 and 2021 has been excluded from this study due to the change in assessment method following the COVID-19 pandemic. To prevent anomalies, when no value was present in a dependent variable, if a zero was present in another, it was deleted. Furthermore, maths and English outcomes were isolated at KS4 and the proportion of facilitating subjects were calculated at KS5 for sensitivity tests. Finally, pupil data was combined into the dataset referenced using URNs to find independent variables such as EHC proportion, number of pupils and local authorities.

Overall, the final dataset consists of 79,476 total observations from 4,898 schools, 49 of which are treated⁷. Control and treated schools may appear in both Key Stages depending on their provision. Table 2 presents the summary statistics for the available variables in the data set.

The independent variables are defined as follows: *Facilitating Subjects* measures the proportion of facilitating subject exams sat, *Pupil Number* states the raw

⁶ Link to data: <https://www.compare-school-performance.service.gov.uk/download-data>

⁷ Treated means the school has been acquired by a private school group.

number of pupils per school, *Income* refers to the annual regional income, *EHC* measures the percentage of pupils with an Education, Health and Care plan, *Examinations Sat* denotes the raw number of examinations taken and *London* represents the percentage of schools located within London boroughs.

Table 2 illustrates fewer observations for maths and English only results. This is attributable to independent schools choosing alternative qualifications to GCSEs called International GCSEs (“iGCSEs”). Independent schools prefer iGCSEs because they function as better preparation for A-Levels through more demanding syllabuses and less coursework whilst not differing in difficulty (Lenon, 2019). iGCSE results are unreported and therefore a reduction in observations is seen in maths and English variables. Dependent variables encompassing all subjects are unaffected because students often only sit iGCSEs for selected subjects. To ensure validity despite a smaller sample size, Table A.2 presents summary statistics for KS4 to demonstrate that with a reduced number of observations the statistics do not majorly differ meaning the smaller sample size will not influence any differences seen in the results section.

There are significant limitations with this dataset. Firstly, if the number of entries from a school for one subject was five or under, the data has been retracted to keep anonymity which has caused a slight reduction in observations. Secondly, there is inconsistent data for alternative examinations schools can choose, for example iGCSEs, BTECs or IB, therefore the study is unable to capture all students. Finally, the largest limitation is the range of variables with unavailable data. This is either because independent schools do not need to declare these, or the public Pupil Census does not disclose them⁸. Data including free school meals, class sizes, attendance or other pupil population variables would allow the study to control for these. Additionally, data for higher education and career prospects or a breakdown of results by socio-economic status, gender or ethnicity could further this study’s analysis to investigate heterogeneous effects. Further

⁸ Full access to Pupil Census data is only attainable at a postgraduate level.

Table 2: Summary Statistics

	Mean	SD	Maximum	Minimum	N
KS4					
Pass Rate %	88.18	15.38	100	0	6,944
High Grades Awarded %	46.14	23.47	100	0	6,930
Average Grade	6.11	1.22	8.89	0.43	6,959
M&E Pass Rate %	86.57	17.43	100	0	3,497
M&E High Grades Awarded %	38.33	22.62	100	0	3,458
M&E Average Grade	5.67	1.15	8.88	0.89	3,497
Pupil Number	480.35	393.77	3,930	0	7,778
Income	38,441.51	4,030.50	45,721.27	32,182.30	8,701
EHC %	3.93	14.28	100	0	7,377
Examinations Sat	384.81	438.40	5,045	0	7,424
London %	20.48	40.36	100	0	8,701
KS5					
Pass Rate %	98.27	4.14	100	0	4,951
High Grades Awarded %	42.56	19.06	100	0	4,951
Average Grade	6.05	1.03	8.75	0.38	4,948
Facilitating Subjects %	61.55	17.17	100	1.27	4,866
Pupil Number	624.08	393.77	3,930	0	5,252
Income	38,370.04	3,822.31	45,721.27	32,182.30	5,665
EHC %	1.06	5.49	100	0	4,759
Examinations Sat	194.15	174.58	1,629	0	5,286
London %	17.28	37.81	100	0	5,665

Notes: SD = Standard Deviation and N = Observations. Variables EHC and Pupil Number have been imputed as explained in 4.2. EHC = Education, Health & Care plan.

studies with greater data availability would be essential in validating this study's results and furthering heterogeneous analysis.

Table 3 presents the balancing table between control and treated groups broken down between Key Stages. Within KS5, it highlights a statistically significant difference between control and treated groups across all independent variables included within this studying, providing statistical reasoning to control for these variables. Similarly, within KS4, all independent variables, apart from EHC, demonstrate a statistically significant difference evidencing these should be controlled for. EHC will also be controlled at KS4 for because it exhibited a statistically significant difference within KS5.

Table 3: Balancing Table

	<u>Control</u>			<u>Treated</u>			Pairwise T-Test
	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	
KS4							
Pupil Number	489.28 (4.5420)	100.14	7,761	351.58 (9.6197)	153.92	256	5.4926***
Income	38411.4 (43.986)	4039.1	8,438	39385.0 (221.6123)	3634.7	269	-3.9033***
EHC	0.0366 (0.0016)	0.1379	7,872	0.0276 (0.0056)	0.0898	258	1.0434
Examinations Sat	386.69 (5.2054)	441.14	7,182	329.11 (22.0804)	343.49	242	2.0099**
KS5							
Facilitating Subjects	0.6173 (0.0025)	0.1695	4,725	0.5546 (0.0190)	0.2262	141	4.2783***
Pupil Number	632.13 (5.3794)	392.731	5,330	347.18 (13.5524)	174.61	166	9.3191***
Income	38340.1 (51.646)	3827.4	5,492	39320.9 (269.0825)	3539.2	173	-3.3262***
EHC	0.0093 (0.0007)	0.0492	5,346	0.0345 (0.0080)	0.1040	169	-6.2378***
Examinations Sat	197.05 (2.4469)	175.21	5,127	100.58 (9.5531)	120.46	159	6.8921***

Notes: Standard Errors in Parathesis. SD = Standard Deviation and N = Observations. Variables EHC and Pupil Number have been imputed as explained in 4.2. EHC = Education, Health & Care plan. Treated are schools owned by a private school group; control are all other independent schools. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

4 Methodology

The analysis aims to comprehensively assess the impact of private school groups on examination results of schools in England. In this section, the methodology and empirical approach are explained.

To evaluate the impact of private school groups on academic achievement this study utilises the staggered difference-in-differences methodology to assess the changes in exam results before and after acquisition. To produce comparable results, this study will focus on Key Stages 4&5. This data is widely available for England, unlike pre-K12 study which lacks standardised tests and is not publicly available. To assess performance three dependent variables are evaluated: average grade, pass rate and high grades awarded.

KS4 is defined as the two years of schooling between ages 14 and 16 when students predominantly sit GCSEs at the end of Year 11. Compulsory subjects include maths, English and science but students have the choice of other GCSEs and usually sit around 10 examinations overall (UCAS, 2025). GCSEs are compulsory for all students which creates a fair comparison.

Comparatively, the two years of schooling between the ages of 16 and 18 is defined as KS5. Legally, students must be in education but have greater choice over what they study; they can take A-Levels, the vocational substitute of T-Levels, an apprenticeship, or equivalent. This study will only examine A-Levels as this is the most selected qualification and is also standardised across England.

OFSTED uses pass rates to assess a school's performance; at GCSE the passing grade is a 4(C) and for A-Level by a grade E. High grade awarded is defined at GCSE by a grade 7(A) and at A-Level by a grade A⁹. This metric is used to differentiate a school's impact on high-achieving and low-achieving students.

To standardise the average grade, alphabetical grades have been translated to numerical grades for both A-Levels and pre-2017 GCSEs using Table A.3. The

⁹ High grades awarded is a metric defined by the author.

conversion in this study has been in accordance with Ofqual guidance equating numerical GCSE grades to alphabetical (Jadhav, 2018).

4.1 Staggered Difference-in-Differences Methodology

The differences-in-differences model estimates the causal effect on a school's attainment through comparing the differences across treated and untreated schools. However, the nature of this study sees unique treatment dates by school, therefore, the basic model cannot be applied as it assumes a singular treatment time. Within literature, the standard difference-in-differences model has historically produced inaccurate results. For example, Card and Krueger's (1994) investigation into the impact of minimum wage increases on employment in the fast-food sector using the difference-in-differences methodology sparked debate over two main problems: forbidden comparisons and treatment effect heterogeneity.

Firstly, Goodman-Bacon (2021) argued that in a differences-in-differences model, some datapoints are temporarily used as controls before they undergo treatment, hereby forming forbidden comparisons. Treated data is therefore being incorrectly compared against data that will be treated later thus it cannot function in the true control group; such comparisons could introduce bias in estimates.

Secondly, Callaway and Sant'Anna (2021) highlighted that treatment effects can be heterogeneous. The effect may differ depending on when treatment was received and basic difference-in-differences cannot estimate how effects evolve dynamically over time.

A previous solution to these problems was the two-way fixed effects ("TWFE") method. This was popularised by Angrist and Pischke (2009) when empirically investigating panel data. They introduced unit fixed-effects to remove time-invariant cofounders and time-fixed effects to control for common shocks; Wooldridge (2010) econometrically justified this. This provided a solution to serial correlation problems in a standard difference-in-differences model (Bertrand *et al.*, 2004) through group fixed-effects and allowed varying treatment times using time fixed-effects (Abadie, 2005). However, Callaway and Sant'Anna (2021) and

Goodman-Bacon (2021) both agreed the TWFE does not provide a solution for forbidden comparisons nor dynamic effects. Additionally, they highlighted TWFE can bias estimates by averaging effects with improper weightings, especially when effects vary within groups.

Since 2020, research into staggered difference-in-differences models has accelerated. Callaway and Sant’Anna (2021) proposed group-time average treatment effects to compare treated groups to untreated data therefore addressing forbidden comparisons. However, this relies heavily on having ample untreated observations, limiting its use in some settings. Additionally, Sun and Abraham (2021) tackled heterogeneous treatment effects by allowing effects to dynamically evolve; their method is computationally intensive therefore may not scale successfully to larger datasets. De Chaisemartin and D’Haultfoeuille (2020) addressed the improper weighting by restructuring comparisons so that later-treated data is not used to control earlier-treated.

On this framework, De Chaisemartin and D’Haultfoeuille (2024) evolved the staggered difference-in-differences model into the ‘did_multiplengt_dyn’ function; this is the primary function utilised within this study using STATA. This is the first function that can estimate staggered differences-in-differences treatment effects for multiple treatment groups with staggered treatment timings and produce dynamic effects which are accurate in empirical research and large panel data. This was an advancement from the function ‘did_multiplengt_stat’ (De Chaisemartin and D’Haultfoeuille, 2020; De Chaisemartin *et al.*, 2022) which was limited to static treatment effects estimators, with no ability to stagger treatment across time.

The staggered difference-in-differences formula:

$$Y_{s,t} = \alpha_s + \delta_t + \sum_l \beta_l D_{s,t-l} + X_{s,t}\gamma + \epsilon_{s,t} \quad (1)$$

Let Y_{st} denote the dependent variable of school s in year t . α_s represents school fixed effects and δ_t represents time fixed effects. $D_{s,t-l}$ represents treatment

exposure for school s in year t minus lag l to allow for dynamic effects while β_l captures the treatment effect at lag l . $X_{s,t}$ implements control variables with γ being a vector of coefficients capturing these effects. Finally, $\varepsilon_{s,t}$ is the error term.

There are two main assumptions in a staggered difference-in-differences model: parallel trends and no-anticipation. The parallel trends assumption states that, without treatment, the trends of the treated and control groups would remain parallel indicating no systematic difference as illustrated in Figure 2. This ensures schools acquired have no underlying characteristics, such as being acquired because they are underperforming. This study anticipates acquisitions are a result of retiring owners or schools being easily acquirable because they are incorporated as private limited companies, factors unrelated to examination results. If parallel trends holds, any post-treatment divergence in trends can be attributed to treatment therefore the assumption is essential when validating the estimates (Angrist and Pischke, 2009; Abadie, 2005; Callaway and Sant’Anna, 2021; Chaisemartin and D’Haultfoeuille, 2024).

Figure 2: Theoretical Difference-in-Differences Model

Notes: Theoretical Staggered Differences-in-Differences diagram presenting differences in treatment (private school groups) and control (all other independent schools) groups before and after treatment.

Additionally, the validity of the difference-in-differences estimates depend on there being no-anticipation (Abbring and Van den Berg, 2003; Malani and Reif, 2015; Botosaru and Gutierrez, 2018; Callaway and Sant’Anna, 2021; Sun and Abraham, 2021, De Chaisemartin and D’Haultfoeuille, 2024). This is where a school’s current outcomes before treatment do not affect the knowledge of future treatment.

De Chaisemartin and D’Haultfoeuille (2024) incorporated testing for parallel trends and no-anticipation within the ‘did_multiplegt_dyn’ function due to the importance of these assumptions in validating the difference-in-differences model’s estimates. The function estimates up to four placebo periods to test whether statistically significant effects are present prior to treatment. The placebo periods should be individually and jointly statistically insignificant indicating no systematic differences in trends between treated and the control group before treatment. Additionally, if no effects were present before treatment, the value zero is expected to be present within the 95% confidence interval, illustrated by the error bars. If the effects were large and statistically significant with a confidence interval not including zero, it would indicate a trend before treatment.

4.2 Empirical Approach

This section outlines the empirical approach employed to ensure the robustness of this study’s results. It justifies the reasoning behind restricting the control group to independent schools, in addition to discussing the implementation of fixed effects, clustering for standard errors, and imputation of missing data. Importantly, the theory behind controlling for independent variables, highlighted in Table 3, is explained below; all possible time-variant independent variables with data have been considered¹⁰.

¹⁰ Full access to Pupil Census data is only attainable at a postgraduate level; future studies with greater access to data could control for more variables.

Selection Bias

Firstly, a threat to validity is selection bias where students are non-randomly assigned to schools based on factors such as socioeconomic status, geography or school selectivity. These endogenous characteristics are confounding variables with academic attainment thus causing casual interference reducing the accuracy of the model's estimates.

Independent schools only serve 6-7% of the population (Sibieta, 2023), largely constrained by tuition fees the therefore attract families with high income, which is correlated with greater educational aspirations and academic attainment (Coulson, 2009; Anders and Henseke, 2021). Moreover, independent schools consistently outperform state schools; in 2024, at GCSE, 48.4% of entries were awarded a grade 7 or higher in independent schools compared to only 21.2% in state schools (The Sutton Trust, 2024).

The control group will be restricted to independent schools therefore reducing heterogeneity and improving validity. However, this approach decreases the sample size, increasing standard errors and limiting generalisability. Accordingly, the unrestricted control group will be included within the sensitivity tests to ensure the robustness of the estimated effects.

Subject Bias

Secondly, another threat to validity is the variation in difficulty across subjects resulting in examination results being incomparable. Since maths and English are compulsory at GCSE, a sensitivity test will be undertaken in which only maths and English will make up the dependent variable.

However, at A-Level, students have flexible choice over subjects. Qingping and Cadwallader (2022) found subject difficulty disparity at A-Level, which is correlated with facilitating subjects (commonly required subjects for further education). Facilitating subjects are science, English, geography, history, mathematics (including further) and modern and classical languages (UCAS, 2024). Qingping and Cadwallader (2022) found 60% of the top 10 and 55% of the

top 20 were facilitating with others included being STEM¹¹ and humanities subjects. To account for subject difficulty at A-Level, a variable will be added to control for the percentage of facilitating subjects taken out of the total examinations sat.

Time and Group Fixed Effects

Thirdly, to prevent bias in estimated treatment effects, unobserved heterogeneity will be controlled for by introducing yearly and school fixed effects.

Potential time-specific shocks include yearly grade trends, the introduction of numerical grades instead of alphabetical for GCSEs between 2017 and 2020, and systematic effects of this study's methodology when converting alphabetical grades to numerical. Additionally, unobserved characteristics that are constant in groups across time are mitigated by controlling for school fixed effects. Potential unobservable differences include socioeconomic status, teaching quality, location, selective status, and a school's culture.

Empirically, Eyles *et al.* (2017) controlled for both school fixed effects and introduced year dummies when investigating the effect of academisation of primary schools in England. The importance of group (school) and time (yearly) fixed effects is highlighted by De Chaisemartin and D'Haultfoeuille (2024) because they automatically introduced these within their 'did_multipligt_dyn' function.

Pupil Number

Next, another time-variant variable that affects attainment is the number of pupils within a school. Lee and Smith (1997) found an optimal high school size for student's education is between 600 and 900 but found a school's size has a stronger effect on lower-SES students and schools with higher concentrations of minority students. Therefore, this study will control for number of students within the robustness section.

¹¹ STEM = Science, technology, engineering and mathematics.

Examinations Sat

The dataset observes a weak correlation between examinations sat and number of pupils, suggesting missing data. At Key Stage 4, this may be attributable to independent schools offering alternative qualifications such as iGCSEs or BTECs and at Key Stage 5 this could include BTECs, International Baccalaureate and T-Levels. To address potential biases from measurement errors within robustness, the number of examinations sat will be controlled for.

Special Educational Needs

Another important time-variant factor is special educational needs and disabilities (“SEND”). SEND pupils consistently and substantially demonstrate lower attainment (Daniel, 2024). In England, there are two SEN classifications: the proportion of student who receive basic SEN support and those with Education, Health and Care (“EHC”) plans, reserved for pupils with more complex needs.

While the dataset provides comprehensive data on EHC plans since their introduction in 2014, the availability of SEN data is limited, particularly for independent schools because they were not required to submit data in the years 2012-2014 and 2016-2018.

To maximise real observations and usable data, this study will control for the proportion of EHC plans and impute the data before 2014 rather than using the incomplete SEN data. Although this may not capture a full spectrum of disabilities, EHC accounts for students with the largest learning barriers which is arguably more meaningful as it is most likely to impact attainment.

Socioeconomic Status

Finally, favourable socioeconomic status (“SES”) including higher income, greater access to resources, opportunities and area of residence are positively correlated with attainment (Liu *et al.*, 2022; Sirin, 2005). Empirically, in difference-in-differences studies, SES is proxied by the proportion of students eligible for free school meals (“FSM”) because it is nationally standardised and correlated with income, parental employment and health (Eyles and Machin, 2019).

However, independent schools are not required to report FSM data meaning FSM cannot be used to control for SES. While this may create omitted variable bias, private schools are unlikely to have a large proportion of deprived students, given the high cost of attendance.

Nevertheless, group fixed effects will address time-invariant SES factors and regional income is the best available variable to provide a broader proxy for SES. Regionally, London and the South-East have stronger examination performance, attributed to parental support and access to resources like private tutoring (Adams, 2024). Despite regional income lacking geographical precision, controlling for regional disparities will increase the accuracy of estimates.

Clustering

To address correlated errors, this study clusters schools at school and local authority levels. Clustering by school accounts for unobserved characteristics and clustering at a local authority level controls for socioeconomic conditions and shared policies; both ensure robustness standard error estimates.

Empirically, studies that use the difference-in-differences methodology to assess US charters and UK academies cluster at a school and local-authority level (Angrist *et al.*, 2013; Bifulco and Ladd, 2006; Eyles and Machin, 2019). Since it is common practice to cluster at the group level, De Chaisemartin and D'Haultfoeuille (2024) integrated group level clustering into the 'did_multipligt_dyn' function.

Imputation

To maintain validity and comparability, absent data must be addressed; smaller sample sizes are incomparable and could generate biased estimates. Zhang (2016) supports the copy mean method to produce reliable estimates and whilst it overlooks inter-variable relationships, the alternative regression-based methods tend to underestimate variability. This means that whilst optimal imputation methods are heavily debated, copy mean methodology is acceptable. Number of pupils is missing in 2014 and 2013; these have been imputed using the

average of 2012 and 2015. Similarly, EHC was introduced in 2015 meaning prior years are missing; the average of 2015-2017 will be imputed into the missing years. As illustrated by Tables 2&3, imputation has meant observations of these variables are similar.

5 Results

In this section, the study's empirical findings will be presented and discussed, evaluating the impact of treatment on GCSE and A-Level results. The analysis will not only examine the overall effect but how these effects differ both within and outside of London and ensure robustness through sensitivity tests.

5.1 Key Stage 4 Results

The overview of the staggered difference-in-differences treatment effects estimates of KS4 are presented in Table 4. These are supplemented with pictures in Figure 3, providing the opportunity to assess the dynamic treatment effects, in addition to evaluating placebo effects, to confirm the parallel trends and no-anticipation assumptions.

Table 4 presents a statistically significant overall decrease of 0.04 in average grade. Additionally, there are contrasting effects between pass rates and high grades awarded; treatment is associated with a 3.4 percentage point decrease in pass rate but a 1.1 percentage point increase in high grades awarded.

In comparison to the summary statistics presented in Table 2, a decrease in average grade by 0.04 grades is negligible when compared to the 'one to nine' scale. Moreover, Figure 3 presents average grade dynamic effects stabilising around zero with no individual period exceeding 0.15 grades difference until the final period. The overall negligible effect is consistent with the literature where autonomous schools predominantly have negligible or negative effects (Irmert *et al.*, 2024).

Comparatively, the effects on pass rates and high grades awarded are economically significant given the respective means of the variables are 88.18%

and 46.14%, but remain relatively small effects. Moreover, the dynamic analysis, illustrated in Figure 3, demonstrates a steady downward trend in pass rate after acquisition whilst high grades awarded fluctuates steadily around zero. Importantly, a decreasing pass rate indicates that, whilst considering the time lag, as school groups invest and implement policies, they are correlated with worsening pass rates. This is consistent with the original hypothesis that as acquisitions increase, the market consolidates, and groups become larger, causing the effect on attainment to become increasingly negative. As discussed, this is likely attributed to groups becoming larger and therefore lose their autonomy and adaptability alongside market consolidation reducing competition and the incentive to improve.

Contradictory to autonomous school literature, KS4 private school groups appear ineffective in supporting low-achieving students. This may reflect low flexibility and adaptability to school-level needs (Eyles and Machin, 2019) or, like UK academies, schools did not need increased autonomy meaning the acquisition was redundant (Eyles *et al.*, 2018) and therefore proving automation does not automatically improve results (Gorard, 2014; Machin and Vernoit, 2011). Simultaneously, the modest increase in high grades awarded demonstrates these policies may disproportionately benefit high-achievers, which is highly inconsistent with literature but does indicate increased educational quality.

Notably, observations in latter periods present narrower error bars across both Key Stages. Figure 1 demonstrates that most acquisitions have occurred within the previous five years, leaving few schools with data in the latter periods. Typically, smaller samples yield greater noise but the opposite is seen here; this limitation may underestimate the model's ability to produce accurate estimates in the later periods, arguing emphasis on earlier periods. Consequently, the final three periods in each model could be anomalies; if these were removed, all dependent variables would improve but would not alter the economic significance of the conclusions from these results. As acquisitions continue, a similar study with greater data could assess dynamic effects more accurately and confirm these results.

As explained, for the difference-in-differences methodology to be valid, the parallel trends and no-anticipation assumptions must hold. This is proven if error bars encompass zero and effects are jointly statistically insignificant. Figure 3 illustrates that two out of three dependent variables include four placebo periods with error bars that include zero confirming the parallel trends assumption. For pass rates, this indicates trends prior to treatment could exist meaning schools acquired have a group characteristic thus not upholding the assumptions and could invalidate the treatment effects. However, a key observation is that the first two placebo periods' error bars encompass zero where these placebos comprise of the largest volume of data arguing greater emphasis could be put on these results.

Table 4: KS4 Main Results

	Pass Rate	High Grades Awarded	Average Grade
Average Total Effect	-0.0343*** (0.0181)	0.0117*** (0.0197)	-0.0381*** (0.1173)
Year & School FE	YES	YES	YES
Observations	6,048	6,037	6,061

*Notes: Estimates produced using the 'did_multipligt_dyn' function on STATA. Standard errors in parenthesis and clustered at a school and local authority level. FEs = School and yearly fixed effects. *p<0.1, **p<0.05, ***p<0.01.*

5.2 Key Stage 5 Results

The estimates from the Key Stage 5 staggered difference-in-differences model are presented in Table 5 with the pictures for each of the dependent variable illustrated in Figure 3. The study finds an overall statistically significant negative decrease of 0.44 average grade in A-Level results, which is substantially larger than the effect on GCSEs. Similarly to KS4, there is a contrast between pass rates and high grades awarded but this contradiction is reversed. Acquisitions are associated with a minimal 0.87 percentage point increase in pass rate but a considerable 7.07 percentage point decrease in high grades awarded, given the

summary statistics presented in Table 2, indicating school group's poor educational quality with high-achieving KS5 students.

Again, the aggregate moderate negative effect on average grade is consistent with the literature regarding autonomous schools as seen in Irmert *et al.* (2024) holistic study. Contrary to KS4, private school groups positively impact low-achievers more than high-achievers which is consistent within the literature, as seen in US charters and UK academies (Angrist *et al.*, 2013; Gleason *et al.*, 2010; Andrews and Perera, 2017).

Arguably, the small pass rate effect is attributable to average pass rates for A-Levels being significantly higher than GCSEs; Table 2 states the means are 88.18% and 98.27% for KS4 and KS5 respectively. With pass rates close to 100% at KS5 a smaller effect is expected because of the minimal possibility of different better results.

Similarly to KS4 pass rates, high grades awarded and average grade at KS5 have persistent downward trends, as presented in Figure 3. This implies the negative effect is a result of structural change from long-term policies as these variables decrease post-time-lag once implemented. Alternatively, as theorised, groups have become larger throughout the periods, therefore losing their autonomy and adaptability, alongside market consolidation reducing competition and removing the incentive to improve.

The significant contrast between the marginal pass rate and the significant decline in high grades suggests school groups prioritize minimum performance thresholds and do not enrich high achiever's education at KS5. Theoretically, this may be a result of resources or investment being reallocated away from high achievers to improve pass rates as seen in US Charters (Angrist *et al.*, 2013). Centralised curriculum and management empirically reduce adaptability (Greany and Higham, 2018) which may assist in stretching high-achieving students. Additionally, profit-incentives may discourage investment in enrichment as evidenced in Chilean Voucher Systems (Miron and Urschel, 2010).

However, the contrast between high and low achievers across Key Stages suggests heterogenous treatment effects cannot be attributed to certain characteristics yet, only theorised. Further investigation is essential before making evidence-based policy recommendations targeting students with different academic abilities.

Similarly to KS4, the final three periods of all models in Figure 3 have comparatively small error bars attributable to lower observations indicating the estimates effects are anomalies; if these were removed all three variables would improve but exhibit no change in economic conclusion.

Figure 3 exhibits zero of the three dependent variables including four placebo periods with error bars that include zero. Again, this indicates the assumptions do not hold questioning the validity of the results. However, similarly all three dependent variables' first two placebo periods' error bars encompass zero indicating the minimal impact of the potential underlying characteristics and arguing that both assumptions hold.

Table 5: KS5 Main Results

	Pass Rate	High Grades Awarded	Average Grade
Average Total Effect	0.0087*** (0.0110)	-0.0707*** (0.0139)	-0.4435*** (0.2053)
Year & School FE	YES	YES	YES
Observations	4,345	4,345	4,354

*Notes: Estimates produced using the 'did_multipligt_dyn' function on STATA. Standard errors in parenthesis and clustered at a school and local authority level. FEs = School and yearly fixed effects *p<0.1, **p<0.05, ***p<0.01.*

Figure 3: Key Stages 4 and 5 difference-in-differences pictures

Notes: Top row presents KS4, and the bottom row presents KS5. Columns from left to right present pass rate, high grades awarded and average grade respectively. Differences-in-Differences model pictures created using the 'did_multilegt_dyn' function on STATA. Clustered at a school and local authority level.

5.3 Heterogeneous Effects

The heterogeneous effects of private school group acquisitions on examination results are assessed across geographical locations. Table 6 details the impact of school group acquisitions through comparing staggered difference-in-differences outcomes from data of schools inside of London to outside¹².

Table 6 presents acquisitions inside of London being associated with a stronger negative effect comparatively across both Key Stages. KS4 pass rate exhibits the largest difference of 7.18 percentage points inside London in comparison to 2.09 percentage points outside. Similarly, the average grade is 0.16 grades lower and high-pass 1.4 percentage points lower inside of London. KS5 exhibits a large regional difference in high grades awarded presenting 10.7 percentage points inside of London compared to 6.5 outside. Comparatively, the difference in KS5 average grades exhibits a decrease of over half a grade in London compared to only one quarter outside London.

While KS5's average grade is consistent with literature, all other dependent variables across both Key Stages are contradictory. Empirically, across US Charters, UK academies and Voucher schools in Chile, urban schools perform better than rural schools. This is attributed, within literature, to greater competition, better access to resources and increased choice (Dobbie and Fryer, 2011; Andrews and Perera, 2017; Contreras *et al.*, 2005).

Theoretically, the contradiction could be explained by greater competition and higher benchmarks in London, causing private school groups to perform comparatively worse. However, additional research is needed to assess reasons or characteristics driving groups to perform worse in urban areas.

Two main observations are present within Figure 4. Firstly, a downward trend is present across both Key Stages, more considerably in KS5, indicating after treatment as policies are implemented and the market consolidates the effect of private school groups worsens, consistent with Figure 3. Secondly, similarly to the results in Table 6, schools inside of London exhibit a larger negative effect indicating they perform worse in urban

¹² A school is classed as inside London if the local authority the school is registered with is a London borough.

areas. Similarly to Figure 3, the later periods in Figure 4 exhibit smaller error bars attributable to lower observations indicating anomalies. If removed, the observed effects strengthen the conclusions discussed above and have no significant economic change.

However, from Figure 4 it is evident that these results may not be valid. The placebo error bars, in London in particular, do not all encompass zero within any model therefore it cannot be confirmed that the parallel trends and no-anticipation assumption hold true, likely due to the small number of observations. Further studies with increased data would confirm validity of these results and conclusions.

Table 6: Geographical Heterogeneous Effects¹³

	KS4		KS5	
	Inside London	Outside London	Inside London	Outside London
Pass Rate				
Average Total Effect	-0.0718*** (0.0233)	-0.0209*** (0.0239)	-0.0128*** (0.0030)	0.0134*** (0.0130)
FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	1,009	4,840	547	3,250
Clusters	31	122	31	122
High Grades Awarded				
Average Total Effect	0.0001*** (0.0242)	0.0138*** (0.0265)	-0.1069*** (0.0093)	-0.0646*** (0.0159)
FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	1,005	4,833	547	3,250
Clusters	31	122	31	122
Average Grade				
Average Total Effect	-0.1666 *** (0.1874)	-0.0065*** (0.1514)	-0.2545*** (0.0619)	-0.5126*** (0.2519)
FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	1,013	4,849	547	3,247
Clusters	31	122	31	122

*Notes: Estimates produced using the 'did_multiplengt_dyn' function on STATA. Standard errors in parenthesis and clustered at a school and local authority level. Inside London defined by whether the schools registered local authority is within a London borough. FEs = School and yearly fixed effects. *p<0.1, **p<0.05, ***p<0.01.*

¹³ Author is aware the number of clusters inside London is on the smaller side of the 'econometric rule of thumb'; Angrist and Pischke (2009) suggest 42 clusters are sufficient meaning 31 may cause inaccuracy.

Figure 4: Key Stages 4&5 Heterogeneous Effects Pictures

Notes: Top row presents KS4 and bottom row KS5. Columns from left to right present pass rate, high grades awarded and average grade respectively. Differences-in-Differences model pictures created using the 'did_multiplengt_dyn' function on STATA. A school is classified in London when the local authority the school is registered at is located within a London Borough. When London = 1 this indicates the school is located within London. Clustered at a school and local authority level.

5.4 Robustness

Finally, a comprehensive set of sensitivity tests were completed to prove the results are robust across unrestricted control groups, additional controls and specific dependent variables, illustrated by Tables 7 and 8. Column 1 for both Tables repeats the main preferred model specification results for both Key Stages.

If pass rate or high grades awarded difference is less than two or one percentage points respectively this will be deemed as negligible. These thresholds are economically insignificant when compared to the summary statistics in Table 2. Similarly, the same applies when average grade differs by less than 0.2 grades.

Subject Discrepancy

Differences in subject difficulty threatens the validity of this study; Qingping and Cadwallader (2022) demonstrate that certain subjects are objectively harder. To control, Column 2 at KS4 restricts the dependent variables to maths and English data only because these subjects are compulsory, whilst at KS5 the proportion of facilitating subjects is controlled for.

In Table 7, a difference of less than 1 percentage point is present within pass rates and high grades awarded, as well as a negligible 0.02 difference in average grade indicating robustness. As previously explained, the significant reduction in observations is attributable to independent schools opting for iGCSEs which are not reported. However, this is unlikely to invalidate results because the summary statistics in Table 2 and Table A.2, where sample size is restricted for all variables, have little differences.

Similarly, in Table 8, pass rate exhibits a less than 0.1 percentage point change, indicating robustness at the lower end of attainment. However, when controlling for subject difficulty, high grades awarded increases by 1.9 percentage points and average grade by 0.15. Arguably, this may indicate private school groups teach harder subjects and therefore the magnitude of their negative effects may not be as large as previously indicated, especially with high achievers, questioning the robustness.

Controls

As described in section 4.2, four controls are implemented in Column 3 to mitigate for potential biases: number of pupils, number of exams sat, regional income and proportion of EHC students.

Table 7 demonstrates pass rate and high grades awarded having less than one percentage point difference between the main results and Column 3 evidencing robustness. Similarly average grade has a negligible decrease of 0.05 grades. Moreover, Table A.4 demonstrates the number of pupils poses the largest threat to validity presenting the largest difference when controlled for. Comparatively, regional income has the smallest impact, as predicted, as it's limited to regional level.

Table 8 demonstrates robustness with controls implemented; pass rates and high grades awarded have a less than one percentage difference and average grade exhibits a negligible increase of 0.03. Furthermore, Table A.5 similarly evidences regional income as having the smallest influence whilst number of pupils accompanied by EHC have the two largest effects, making them greatest threats to validity.

Unrestricted Control Group

In Column 4, the control group is unrestricted to include all schools registered in England to expand the sample size therefore increasing the validity of the results. Reassuringly, in both Tables 7 and 8 the estimated effects of the unrestricted control group have negligible differences across all dependent variables with respect to the main results, whilst remaining statistically significant, therefore evidencing robustness.

Unrestricted Control Groups with Controls

Column 5 combines the unrestricted control group (Column 4) with the controls introduced (Column 3) to provide a holistic view on robustness.

Table 7 illustrates at KS4 a negligible difference in average grade of only 0.055 grades. Both pass rates and high grades awarded exhibit minimal differences below the discussed thresholds indicating robustness.

Similarly, at KS5, demonstrated by Table 8, negligible discrepancies are present across all dependent variables per the threshold set out above conclusively proving robustness.

Overall, the robustness tests presented in Tables 7&8 provide strong reassurance that the results are stable across alternative control groups and controls which reinforces the reliability of the conclusions regarding the impact of school group acquisitions on examination results.

Table 7: KS4 Robustness

	Main Results	Maths & English only	Four Controls added	Unrestricted Control group	Controls added & full dataset
Pass Rate					
Average Total Effect	-0.0343*** (0.0181)	-0.0401*** (0.0093)	-0.0450*** (0.0169)	-0.0368*** (0.0179)	-0.0503*** (0.0166)
FES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	6,048	2,666	5,892	31,612	31,213
High Grades Awarded					
Average Total Effect	0.0117*** (0.0197)	0.0078*** (0.0158)	0.0116*** (0.0236)	0.0101*** (0.0194)	0.0083*** (0.0239)
FES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	6,037	2,615	5,892	31,542	31,213
Average Grade					
Average Total Effect	-0.0381*** (0.1173)	-0.0402*** (0.0637)	-0.0916*** (0.1143)	0.0368*** (0.1163)	-0.0929*** (0.1131)
FES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	6,061	2,666	5,906	32,208	31,807

Notes: Estimates calculated using the 'did_multiplengt_dyn' function on STATA. Standard Errors in parenthesis and clustered at a school and local authority level. Main results as in Table 4. Unrestricted control group includes all schools in England. Controls added are number of pupils, percentage of EHC, exams sat and regional income. EHC = Education, Health and Care plans. FEs = School and yearly fixed effects. *p<0.1, **p<0.05, ***p<0.01.

Table 8: KS5 Robustness

	Main Results	Controlling for facilitating Subjects	Additional Four Controls added	Unrestricted Control group	Controls added & full dataset
Pass Rate					
Average Total Effect	0.0087*** (0.0110)	0.0086*** (0.0143)	-0.0011*** (0.0075)	0.0140*** (0.0108)	0.0029*** (0.0090)
FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	4,345	3,822	3,743	19,716	16,326
High Grades Awarded					
Average Total Effect	-0.0707*** (0.0139)	-0.0517*** (0.0151)	-0.0642*** (0.0183)	-0.0772*** (0.0139)	-0.0675*** (0.0259)
FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	4,345	3,822	3,743	19,716	16,326
Average Grade					
Average Total Effect	-0.4435*** (0.2053)	-0.2901*** (0.2665)	-0.4111*** (0.2049)	-0.4592*** (0.2042)	-0.4281*** (0.1980)
FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	4,354	3,822	3,743	19,798	16,324

Notes: Estimates calculated using the 'did_multiplengt_dyn' function on STATA. Standard Errors in parenthesis and clustered at a school and local authority level. Main results as in Table 5. Unrestricted control group includes all schools in England. Controls added are number of pupils, percentage of EHC, exams sat and regional income. EHC = Education, Health and Care plans. FEs = School and yearly fixed effects. *p<0.1, **p<0.05, ***p<0.01.

6 Conclusion

This study is the first empirical research on the impact of private school groups on Key Stages 4&5 academic attainment in England. Utilising a staggered difference-in-differences methodology, validated with robustness checks, the study finds compelling evidence that acquisitions are associated with a statistically significant negative impact on academic performance. These results are economically significant at KS5 where average grade declines by nearly half a grade whilst at KS4 they are negligible. This is consistent with literature of similar systems finding mixed but slightly negative results.

Additionally, the results reveal contrasting effects; at KS4 falling pass rates are contrasted with a modest rise in high grades whilst at KS5 a small improvement in pass rates is accompanied by a substantial drop in high grades. Our results imply reduced school-level autonomy and profit incentives may constrain responsiveness to local needs and hinder attainment. However, the small differences in pass rates indicate private school groups comparatively assist low-achieving students more than others.

Interestingly, negative effects are more pronounced inside of London, contradicting prior research that autonomous schools perform better in urban areas. This indicates the level of competition, access to resources, and networks can play a critical role in impacting education.

Whilst the methodology was designed to ensure robustness, several limitations persist. The result only reflects the aggregate impact of all private school groups which, while similar, all differ in policy, global presence and ethos. Further research into individual group's impacts would be valuable in isolating policies that positively impact education. Additionally, as private school groups are continually growing, future years of data and research are required to validate the findings of this study, so that a longitudinal observation of the treatment effects can be ascertained. Finally, attainment is not the sole component of educational quality; character development and holistic student growth are not captured within this study but are still considered educational components.

Nevertheless, this study provides evidence that current private school groups do not significantly improve academic outcomes and, in some cases, worsen them, particularly in high-performing, competitive urban areas. This suggests regulators should consider restricting the rapid growth of private school groups and prevent monopolies as well as parents reassessing whether these schools are optimal for their children given their potential negative results.

7 Bibliography

Abadie, A., 2005. Difference-in-Differences with variation in treatment timing. *Journal of Econometrics*, 225(2), pp. 254-277.

Abbring, J., Van den Berg, G., 2003. The nonparametric identification of treatment effects in duration models. *Econometrica*, 71(5), pp. 1491-1517.

Abdulkadiroglu, A., Angrist, J., Dynarski, S., Kane, T., Pathak, P., 2011. Accountability and flexibility in public schools: Evidence from Boston's charters and pilots. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 126(2), pp. 699-748.

Adams, R., 2024. *Pupils achieve best A-level results in a generation but regional gap widens* [Online]. UK: The Guardian. Available from: <https://www.theguardian.com/education/article/2024/aug/15/pupils-achieve-best-a-level-results-in-a-generation-as-regional-disparity-gap-widens> [Accessed 27th January 2025].

Anders, J., Henseke, G., 2021. *Housing wealth, not bursaries, explains much of private school participation for those without high income* [Online]. UK: University College London. Available from: <https://blogs.ucl.ac.uk/ioe/2021/02/08/housing-wealth-not-bursaries-explains-much-of-private-school-participation-for-those-without-high-income/> [Accessed 6 March 2025].

Andrews, M., Duncombe, W., Yinger., 2002. Revisiting economies of size in American education: Are we any closer to a consensus? *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*, 5(4), pp 1-27.

Andrews, J., Perera, N., 2017. *The impact of academies on educational outcomes*. UK: Education Policy Institute.

Angrist, J., Bettinger, E., Bloom, E., King, E., Kremer, M., 2002. Vouchers for Private Schooling in Columbia: Evidence from a Randomized Natural Experiment. *The American Economic Review*, 92(5), pp. 1535-1558.

Angrist, J., Pischke, J., 2009. *Mostly Harmless Econometrics: An Empiricist's Companion*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.

Angrist, J., Pathak, P., Walters, C., 2013. Explaining charter school effectiveness. *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*, 5(4), pp. 1-27.

Angrist, J., Cohodes, S., Dynarski, S., Pathak, P., Walters, C., 2016. Stand and Deliver: Effects of Boston's Charter High Schools on College Preparation, Entry and Choice. *Journal of Labour Economics*, 34(2), pp. 275-318.

Barro, R., 2013. Education and Economic Growth. *Annals of economics and finance*, 14(2), pp. 301-328.

- Becker, G., 1964. *Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Behrman, J., Parker, S., Todd, P., 2016. Do private schools increase student achievement? Evidence from a voucher programme in Chile. *Journal of Public Economics*, 91(6), pp. 1075-1098.
- Bellei, C., 2009. Does voucher education work? Evidence on a natural experiment in Chile. *Comparative Education Review*, 53(2), pp. 139-158.
- Bertrand, M., Duflo, E., Mullainathan, S., 2004. How much should we trust differences-in-differences estimates?. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 119(1), pp. 249-275.
- Bettinger, E. P. (2005). The effect of charter schools on charter students and public schools. *Economics of Education Review*, 24(2), pp. 133–147.
- Bifulco, R., Ladd, H., 2006. The Impacts of Charter Schools on Student Achievement: Evidence From North Carolina. *Education Finance and Policy*, 1(1), pp. 50-90.
- Blundell, R., Dearden, L., Sibiet, L., 2010. *The demand for private schooling in England: the impact of price and quality*. UK: ESRC.
- Böhlmark, A., Lindhal, M., 2015. Independent schools and long-run educational outcomes: Evidence from Sweden's large-scale voucher reform. *Economics of Education Review*, 46, pp. 109-122.
- Botosaru, I., Gutierrez, F., 2018. Differences-in-differences when the treatment status is observed in only one period. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 33(1), pp. 73-90.
- Callaway, B., Sant'Anna, P., 2021. Difference-in-Differences with multiple time periods. *Journal of Econometrics*, 225(2), pp. 200-230.
- Card, D., Krueger, A., 1994. Minimum Wages and Employment: A Case Study of the Fast-Food Industry in New Jersey and Pennsylvania. *The American Economic Review*, 84(4), pp. 772-793.
- Contreras, D., Sepúlveda, P. and Bustos, S., 2010. When schools are the ones that choose: The effects of screening in Chile. *Social Science Quarterly*, 91(5), pp.1349-1368.
- Cognita, 2025. *Become a Cognita School* [Online]. United Kingdom: Cognita. Available from: <https://www.cognita.com/become-a-cognita-school/> [Accessed 2 February 2025].
- CREDO, 2013. *National Charter School Study 2013*. USA: Stanford University.
- Chodes, S., 2018. *Charter Schools and the Achievement Gap*. USA: Princeton-Brookings.

Companies House, 2025. *Companies House*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/companies-house> [Accessed 15 February 2025].

Coulson, A., 2009. Comparing Public, Private, and Market Schools: The International Evidence. *The Journal of School Choice*, 3(1), pp. 31-54.

Cullen, J., Jacob, B., Levitt, S., 2005. The impact of school choice on student outcomes: Evidence from a social experiment in charter schools. *Econometrica*, 73(5), pp. 1191-1230.

Daniel, J., 2024. The academic achievement gap between students with and without special educational needs and disabilities. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, pp. 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2024.2400771>.

De Chaisemartin, C., D’Haultfoeuille, X., 2020. Two-Way Fixed Effects Estimators with Heterogenous Treatment Effects. *American Economic Review*, 110(9), pp. 2964-2996.

De Chaisemartin, C., D’Haultfoeuille, X., Pasquier, F., Vazquez-Bare, G., Sow, D., 2022. Difference-in-Difference for Continuous Treatments and Instruments with Stayers. Available at SSRN: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4011782>

De Chaisemartin, C., D’Haultfoeuille, X., 2024. Difference-in-Differences Estimators of Intertemporal Treatment Effects. *Forthcoming, Review of Economics and Statistics*. Available at SSRN: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3731856>

Dobbie, W., Fryer, R., 2011. Are High-Quality Schools Enough to Increase Achievement Among the Poor? Evidence from the Harlem Children’s Zone. *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*, 3(3), pp. 158-187.

Dobbie, E., Fryer, R., 2013. Getting beneath the veil of effective schools: evidence from New York City. *American Economic Journal: Applies Economics*, 5(4), pp. 28-60.

Dukes Education, 2025. *What is Dukes?* [Online]. United Kingdom: Dukes Education. Available from: <https://dukeseducation.com/what-we-do/#:~:text=Our%20students%20benefit%20from%20the,experience%20and%20expertise%20in%20education> [Accessed 2 February 2025].

Education Investor, 2025. *Education Investor Global*. Available at: <https://educationinvestor.co.uk/> [Accessed 15 February 2025].

Education Policy Institute, 2017. *School Performance in academies vs maintained schools: An evidence review*. London: Education Policy Institute.

Elacqua, D., 2012. The impact of school choice on student outcomes: Evidence from Chile. *Education Economics*, 20(3), pp. 300-323.

Eyles, A., Machin, S., McNally, S., 2017. Unexpected school reform: Academisation of primary schools in England. *Journal of Public Economics*, 155, pp. 108-121.

Eyles, A., Machin, S., Silva, O., 2018. Academies 2 – The New Batch. *Fiscal Studies*. 39(1), pp. 121-158.

Eyles, A., Machin, S., 2019. The introduction of academy schools to England's education. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 17(4), pp. 1107-1146.

Forfar Education, 2025. *What we offer* [Online]. UK: Forfar Education. Available from: <https://www.forfareducation.co.uk/page/?title=What+We+Offer&pid=7> [Accessed 2 February 2025].

Gleason, P., Clark, M., Tuttle, C., and Dwoyer, E. (2010). *The evaluation of charter school impacts: Final report*. Washington, D.C.: National Center for Education Evaluation and Regional Assistance, Institute of Education Sciences, U.S. Department of Education (No. NCEE 2010-4029).

Goodman-Bacon, A., 2021. Difference-in-differences with variation in treatment timing. *Journal of Econometrics*, 225(2), pp. 254-277.

Gorard, S., 2014. The academies programme: Another wrong turn?. *Journal of Education Policy*, 29(5), pp. 567-582.

Greany, T., Higham, R., 2018. *Hierarchy, Markets and Networks: Analysing the 'self-improving school-led system' agenda in England and the implications for schools*. London: UCL Institute of Education Press.

Hanushek, C., Woessmann, L., 2008. The role of cognitive skills in economic development. *Journal of economic literature*, 46(3), pp. 607-668.

Haves, E., 2023. *Improving School's performance: are multi-academy trusts the answer?* [Online]. UK: House of Lords Library. Available from: <https://lordslibrary.parliament.uk/improving-schools-performance-are-multi-academy-trusts-the-answer/> [Accessed 28 January 2025].

Hoxby, C., 2000. Does Competition among public schools benefit students and taxpayers? *American Economic Review*, 90(5), pp. 1209-1238.

Hoxby, C., Murarka, S., 2009. *Charter schools in New York City: who enrolls and how they affect their students' achievement* (NBER Working Paper No. 14852). Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research.

Hsieh, C., Urquiola, M., 2006. The Effects of Generalized school choice on achievement and stratification: Evidence from Chile's Voucher Program. *Journal of Public Economics*, 90(9), pp. 1477-1503.

IBIS, 2024. *General Secondary Education in the UK*. (UK P85.310) UK: IBIS.

Inspired Education, 2025. *Our Inspired approach to education* [Online]. UK: Inspired Education. Available from: <https://www.inspirededu.com/education-learning/our-philosophy> [Accessed 2 February 2025].

Irmert, N., Bietenbeck, J., Mattisson, L., Weinhardt, F., 2024. *Autonomous Schools, Achievement, and Segregation*. IZA Discussion Paper No, 17462. Bonn: IZA – Institute of Labour Economics.

Jadhav, C., 2018. *GCSE 9 to 1 grades: a brief guide for parents* [Online]. United Kingdom: Department of Education. Available from: <https://ofqual.blog.gov.uk/2018/03/02/gcse-9-to-1-grades-a-brief-guide-for-parents/>. [Accessed 16 November 2024].

Lee, V., Smith, J., 1997. High School Size: Which works Best and for Whom?. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 19(3), pp. 205-227.

Lenon, B., 2019. *Key points to remember about iGCSEs* [Online]. United Kingdom: Independent Schools Council. Available from: <https://www.isc.co.uk/media-enquiries/news-press-releases-statements/key-points-to-remember-about-igcse/> [Accessed 4 April 2025].

Lindbom, A., 2010. School Choice in Sweden: Effects on student performance, school costs, and segregation. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 54(2), pp. 161-178.

Lubienski, C., Brewer, T., 2016. *Learning to teach in an era of privatisation: Global trends in teacher preparation*. New York Teachers College Press.

Lubienski, C., Lubienski, S., 2014. *The Public School Advantage: Why Public Schools Outperform Private Schools*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Lui, J., Peng, P., Zhao, B., Luo, L., 2022. Socioeconomic Status and Academic Achievement in Primary and Secondary Education: A Meta-analytic Review. *Educational Psychology Review*, 34, pp. 2867-2896.

Machin, S., Veroit, J., 2011. *The impact of academy schools on pupil outcomes*. London: Centre for Economic Performance. London: London School of Economics.

Malani, A., Reif, J., 2015. Interpreting pre-trends as anticipation: Impact on estimated treatment effects from tort reform. *Journal of Public Economics*, 124(1), pp. 1-17.

Market IQ, (2025) *Market IQ Database*. Available at: https://www.secure-marketiq.com/users/sign_in [Accessed 15 February 2025].

Miron, G., Urschel, J., 2010. *Equal or fair? A study of revenue and expenditure in American Charter Schools*. USA: Education and the Public Interest Centre & Education Policy research unit, Arizona State University.

- Miron, G., Urschel, J., Mathis, W., Tornquist, E., 2011. *Schools without Diversity: Education Management Organizations, Charter Schools and the Demographic Stratification of the American School System*. USA: National Education Policy Center.
- Muijs, D., Ainscow, M., Chapman, C., West, M., 2021. *Collaboration and Networking in Education*. London: Routledge.
- Nord Anglia Education, 2025. *Nord Anglia Education* [Online]. United Kingdom: Nord Anglia Education. Available from: <https://www.nordangliaeducation.com/> [Accessed 2 February 2025].
- OECD, 2018. *Education at a Glance 2018* [Online]. Paris: OECD. Available from: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2018/09/education-at-a-glance-2018_g1g921ab.html [Accessed 12 March 2025].
- OECD, 2024. *Survey of Adults Skills 2023: England (United Kingdom)* [Online]. Paris: OECD. Available from: [https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/survey-of-adults-skills-2023-country-notes_ab4f6b8c-en/united-kingdom_02bc78e4-en.html#:~:text=2.1..average\)%20\(Figure%201\)](https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/survey-of-adults-skills-2023-country-notes_ab4f6b8c-en/united-kingdom_02bc78e4-en.html#:~:text=2.1..average)%20(Figure%201)). [Accessed 12 March 2025].
- Parry, T., 2006. Theory Meets Reality in the Education Voucher Debate: Some Evidence from Chile. *Education Economics*, 5(3), pp 307-331.
- Qingping, H., Cadwallader, S., 2022. *Inter-subject comparability in GCSEs and A levels in summer 2022*. UK: Ofqual.
- Rivkin, S., Hanushek, E., Kain, J., 2005. Teachers, Schools and Academic Achievement. *Econometrica*, 73(2), pp. 417-458.
- Sibieta, L., 2023. *Tax, private school fees and state school spending*. (IFS Report R263). UK: Institute for Fiscal Studies.
- Sirin, S., 2005. Socioeconomic Status and Academic Achievement: A Meta-Analysis Review of Research. *Review of Educational Research*, 75(3), pp. 417-453.
- Sun, L., Abraham, S., 2021. Estimating dynamic treatment effects in event studies with heterogeneous effects. *Journal of Econometrics*, 225(5), pp. 175-199.
- The Sutton Trust, 2024. *Sutton Trust response to GCSE Results Day 2024* [Online]. UK: The Sutton Trust. Available from: <https://www.suttontrust.com/news-opinion/all-news-opinion/sutton-trust-response-to-gcse-results-day-2024/> [Accessed 6 March 2025].
- UCAS, 2024. *Planning their future* [Online]. UK: UCAS. Available from: <https://www.ucas.com/discover/advice-parents-guardians-and-carers/planning-their-future> [Accessed 6 November 2024].
- UCAS, 2025. *How to advise students about GCSE choices* [Online]. UK: UCAS. Available from: <https://www.ucas.com/advisers/help-and-training/develop-your-skills->

[adviser/how-advise-students-about-gcse-choices#:~:text=How%20many%20GCSE%20subjects%20is,than%20ten%20can%20be%20counterproductive.](#) [Accessed 6 March 2025].

Urquiola, M., 2005. Does School Choice lead to Sorting? Evidence from Tiebout Variation. *American Economic Review*, 95(4), pp. 1310-1326.

Wooldridge, J., 2010. *Econometric Analysis of Cross Section and Panel Data*. 2nd Edition. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

Wishford Education, 2025. *About Wishford* [Online]. UK: Wishford Education. Available from: <https://wishford.co.uk/about/> [Accessed 2 February 2025].

Zhang, Z., 2016. Missing data imputation: focusing on single imputation. *Annals of Translational Medicine*, 4(1), pp. 1-8.

Zimmer, R., Gill, B., Booker, K., Lavertu, S., Sass, T., Witte, J., 2009. *Charter Schools in Eight States: Effects on Achievement, Attainment, Integration and Competition*. Santa Monica, CA: RAND Corporation.

8 Appendix

Table A.1 Private School Group's Overview

Private School Group	Global Schools	UK Schools	Schools included in this study	Institutional Investor	Countries
Cognita	106	39	10	Jacobs Holdings AG	16
Alpha Schools	19	19	6	3i and Downing Ventures	1
Dukes	54	35	8	Universities Superannuation Scheme (USS)	8
Inspired Education	115	19	3	Oakley Capital	24
Inspired Learning Group	27	27	5	Bridgepoint and Stonepeak	1
Nord Anglia	82	4	3	EQT, CPP Investments and Neuberger Berman	33
Chatsworth Schools	17	15	4	Synova Capital	1
Globeducate	61	5	2	CDPQ	11
Forfar Education	13	13	1	Mubadala Investment Company	1
Wishford Education	20	20	1	Patron Capital & Wishford Foundation	1
Bellevue Education	19	17	3	GEMS Education (CVC Capital Partners)	3
International School Partnership	105	1	1	OMERS PE	25

Notes: Schools included in this study only includes Key Stages 4 & 5 whereas UK & Global schools encompass all Key Stages. Institutional Investor states notable investors. Author created this table using data from Education Investor (2024), MarketIQ (2024) and Companies House (2024).

Table A.2: KS4 Restricted Summary Statistics

	Mean	SD	Maximum	Minimum	N
Pass Rate %	85.91	15.73	100	1.54	3,465
High Grades Awarded %	39.66	20.81	100	0	3,465
Average Grade	5.81	1.12	8.85	0.90	3,473
M&E Pass Rate %	86.57	17.43	100	0	3,497
M&E High Grades Awarded %	38.33	22.62	100	0	3,458
M&E Average Grade	5.67	1.15	8.88	0.89	3,497
Pupil Number	404.44	341.57	3930	9	3,243
Income	38,221.64	4,073.01	45,721.27	32,182.3	3,497
EHC %	2.90	11.01	100	0	2,820
Examinations Sat	441.98	531.42	4,772	6	3,497
London %	20.07	40.06	100	0	3,497

Notes: Iteration from Table 2 but dropped observations if the Maths and English Pass rate was missing. SD = Standard Deviation and N = Observations. Variables EHC and Pupil Number have been imputed as explained in 4.3. EHC = Education, Health & Care plan.

Table A.3: Alphabetical grade conversion

Alphabetical Grade	GCSE		A-level Numerical Conversion
	Numerical Conversion	Numerical Conversion	
A*	9	9	
A	7	7.5	
B	5.5	6	
C	4.5	4.5	
D	3	3	
E	2	1.5	
F	1.5	0	
G	1	N/A	
U	0	N/A	
No Result	0	0	

Notes: GCSE grades gradually changed from alphabetical to numerical between 2017-2020. Conversion is completed at A-Level to make average grade numerical to analyse and compare. Conversion based on Ofqual guidance (Jadhav, 2018).

Table A.4: KS4 Broken down effects of control variables

	Number of Pupils	Examinations Sat	EHC	Income
Pass Rate				
Average Total Effect	-0.0382*** (0.0189)	-0.0401*** (0.0157)	-0.0384*** (0.0195)	-0.0341*** (0.0181)
FES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	5,968	6,033	5,913	6,048
High Grades Awarded				
Average Total Effect	0.0083*** (0.0206)	0.0093*** (0.0201)	0.0144*** (0.0207)	0.0119*** (0.0198)
FES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	5,957	6,033	5,902	6,037
Average Grade				
Average Total Effect	-0.0720*** (0.1205)	-0.0670*** (0.1052)	-0.0590*** (0.1256)	-0.0373*** (0.1175)
FES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	5,981	6,046	5,927	6,061

Notes: Standard Errors in parenthesis and clustered at a school and local authority level. EHC = Education, Health and Care plans. FEs = School and yearly fixed effects. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Table A.5: KS5 Controls broken down

	Number of Pupils	Examinations Sat	EHC	Income
Pass Rate				
Average Total Effect	0.0002*** (0.0071)	0.0088*** (0.0150)	-0.0037*** (0.0057)	0.0083*** (0.0108)
FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	4,294	4,334	4,272	4,345
High Grades Awarded				
Average Total Effect	-0.0807*** (0.0166)	-0.0708*** (0.0143)	-0.0874*** (0.0149)	-0.0715*** (0.0138)
FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	4,294	4,334	4,272	4,345
Average Grade				
Average Total Effect	-0.5891*** (0.2789)	-0.4755*** (0.3419)	-0.6324*** (0.1991)	-0.4765*** (0.2171)
FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	4,292	4,334	4,270	4,343

Notes: Standard Errors in parenthesis and clustered at a school and local authority level. EHC = Education, Health and Care plans. FEs = School and yearly fixed effects. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.